

Effect of classical music vs. rock music on gene expression patterns in *Oryza sativa*

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Abstract

*This study delves into the fascinating connection between music and plant behaviour, specifically focusing on how classical and rock music affect *Oryza sativa*. Using careful experiments, we investigate how these different musical styles influence gene expression and growth in these plants. In special music chambers, we exposed *Oryza sativa* to classical and rock music separately. This unique setup allowed us to explore how the plants react to different musical sounds and rhythms. Our analysis of gene expression in *Oryza sativa* exposed to both types of music yielded intriguing results. For instance, the gene *rbcS*, which is crucial for photosynthesis, responded differently. Classical music led to a small increase in its expression after 20 days, while rock music caused a distinct change that set it apart from both the control group and the classical music group.*

*This suggests that the two types of music can affect how well *Oryza sativa* carries out photosynthesis. Looking deeper, we found that the *XTH8* gene, linked to cell wall remodelling, responded more to classical music. This echoes findings from similar genes in other plants, hinting at a universal connection between sound vibrations and plant structure. On the other hand, rock music triggered a different pattern, emphasizing how the two genres can create unique effects in plants. Lastly, the *AGPL* gene, which is tied to starch production, reacted more to classical music on day 20. This could mean that classical music might help these plants store more energy. In contrast, rock music led to a different response, again highlighting the distinct impact of the genre.*

Keywords: Gene expression, *Oryza sativa*, music.

Introduction

The skepticism of humanity towards the idea that plants possess senses similar to ours, arises from our tendency to perceive nature through the lens of our own understanding. Plants have already demonstrated their ability to sense touch, so the idea that they could also sense music came into highlight. Studies from as early as the 1950s on plant acoustics provided controversial reports of the claim that music had an effect on plants⁸. Plants are continuously under the influence of various stresses from environmental factors and due to their inability to move, plants have developed

various mechanisms to utilize the conditions and factors to modulate their survival and growth during the course of evolution.

Due to the continuous evolutionary pressure, plants have evolved to obtain sensitivity to biotic and abiotic stimuli such as pathogen attack, injury, light, temperature etc. Besides these, plants have also developed sensitivity towards physical and mechanical factors including rain, wind, touch and vibrations⁴. "Music is not ecologically relevant for plants, but there are sounds that could be advantageous for them to hear," a quote by Chamovitz² is highly relevant. Across environmental niches, every region inhabited by plants is surrounded by vibrations originating from biological sources such as chirping of birds, animal cries, buzzing of bees, insect stridulation etc. along with physical sources including brushing of leaves by the wind, water droplets during rain etc.

As a result, plants have undeniably developed a sensitivity towards sound vibrations (SV) of various ecologically relevant frequencies and decibels. Direct evidence of this is an amazing phenomenon termed 'buzz pollination' where pollens are released from anthers only upon inducing vibrations of a particular frequency produced by buzzing bees⁷. Research has also elucidated the response of *Arabidopsis* to mount a defence response by accumulating defence molecules upon treatment of sound vibrations caused by the churning sound of caterpillars¹. The potential beneficial effect of sound on plants has been claimed by various researchers, although it has been a topic of contradictions and debate for decades²³. Researchers argued on the complexity of music, having combinations of various frequencies, tones and amplitudes, but it may not have any evolutionary significance. However, certain natural music, sometimes termed 'green music' like cricket's stridulating, bird's chirping and bee buzzing have proved to be important³.

Research has shown that green music increased oxygen uptake and polyamine content in Chinese cabbage²⁰. The beneficial effect of ultrasound on callus regeneration, suspension culture and plant transformation has also been elucidated⁶. In recent years, sound vibrations (SV) have been widely implicated in agriculture for facilitating crop growth and yield by virtue of its growth-enhancing effects and resistance capabilities. Plant acoustic frequency technology (PAFT) improved growth, provided disease resistance and increased photosynthetic characteristics in various vegetables¹¹. Developmental and physiological processes of plants including cell cycle progression, seed germination,

growth, plasma membrane architecture were reported to change by sounds in the range of audible frequencies¹⁷.

The postharvest shelf life of tomato was also reported to increase with the use of sound vibrations. When treated with SVs of 1000 Hz, ripening was delayed compared to untreated controls¹⁶. Repressive histone modifications increased at the RIN, NOR and TAGL1 genes, which are positive regulators of fruit ripening, while transcriptional activation histone modifications decreased by sound waves. The genes that code for the enzymes that produce ethylene, have also shown similar epigenetic processes. The use of sound waves increased the expression of histone modification enzyme genes involved in H3 methylation and deacetylation while decreasing the expression of those involved in H3 acetylation and demethylation.

Furthermore, histone-modifying enzymes may physically engage with transcription factors to form direct associations with the promoters of the genes RIN, NOR and TAGL1 and indirect associations with the promoters of the genes for ethylene biosynthetic enzymes¹⁵. Even though different species have evolutionarily developed different structures to perceive sound, the processing and response mechanisms appear to be more-or-less similar. The physical properties of sound waves provide an explanation to this claim. Sound waves originate from objects vibrating and are transmitted through the medium they travel through by oscillation of the particles in the medium. Potentially, these waves can vibrate any object interfaced with. Even in animals with ears, it is the vibration of the eardrum that is the key factor responsible for sound perception⁹.

Various mechano-sensitive channels are equipped on plant membranes that are believed to be responsive to mechanical vibrations¹³. The tension in biological membranes might be altered by sound vibrations which has the potential to evoke a signalling cascade by the activation of these channels¹². The exact mechanism by which a plant cell is sensitized mechanically to these SVs is still not properly understood.

However, it is believed that the interface of plant cell wall and membrane play a role in mechanical stimulus perception and leads to a cascade of events. Upon mechanical stimulus, cytoskeleton activity opens various stretch-activated ion channels on the membranes of the cell^{11,23}.

Ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase (Rubisco) catalyzes the rate-limiting step of CO₂ fixation in photosynthesis, but O₂ competes with CO₂ for substrate ribulose 1,5-bisphosphate, leading to the loss of fixed carbon. Rubisco is composed of only two kinds of subunits, a nuclear multigene family-encoded small subunit (*rbcS*) and a chloroplast-encoded large subunit (*rbcL*)²².

The class of enzymes classified as xyloglucan endotransglycosylases/hydrolases (*XTHs*) is involved in the formation and remodelling of cellulose/xyloglucan crosslinks and is crucial for regulating cell wall extensibility¹⁸. The significance of this gene family in the control of cell wall extensibility has been emphasized in a number of studies. According to research, hormones are crucial for fine-tuning *XTH* activity during plant growth and the enzyme activity may fluctuate in response to environmental changes such as abiotic stressors¹⁸.

Figure 1: A model summarizing the molecular events triggered within a plant cell upon stimulation by sound vibrations (SVs) (Modified from Ghosh et al¹⁰)

ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylase is involved in catalyzing the first and limiting step in starch biosynthesis and is allosterically regulated by 3-phosphoglycerate and phosphate levels in plants. ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylases are heterotetramers composed of two types of subunits, small and large. The small subunit (SS) is responsible for the catalytic activity whereas the large subunit (LS) plays a regulatory function⁵.

Rice is a staple food for many countries worldwide and a great source of carbohydrate. Paddy rice treated with SVs of 400 Hz frequency and 106 dB showed a significant increase in shoot height, weight, root system activity, germination index and permeability of cell membrane. However, upon inducing frequencies above this range, harmful effects were recorded, suggesting sound vibrations at an optimal level have the capability to enhance the cell's physiological activity²³.

With the use of sound vibrations in agricultural practices, the use of fertilizers could be potentially reduced by 25%. SV treatments have been found to increase immunological responses against plant pathogens and pests as well. This was highlighted by the study reporting the spread of sheath blight in rice was reduced by 50% upon treatment by sound vibrations⁶.

Over the course of several decades, the widespread utilization of chemical fertilizers and pesticides has witnessed a dramatic escalation, primarily driven by their affordability and accessibility. However, the extensive use of synthetic fertilizers has led to a deterioration in soil health, precipitating adverse consequences such as aquatic pollution and the phenomenon of biomagnification.

Furthermore, the emergence and proliferation of pesticide resistance, along with the associated undesirable effects, have been the subject of extensive investigation over time. It is noteworthy that the application of pesticides and insecticides also engenders collateral damage by eradicating beneficial organisms critical for ecosystem equilibrium.

In response to these concerns, increasing attention is being devoted to the potential of sound vibrations (SVs) to assume a multifaceted role in bolstering agricultural yield, fortifying resistance against diseases and extending the post-harvest shelf life of agricultural commodities. Consequently, the present experiment seeks to unveil the potential implications of SVs on the cultivation practices of *Oryza sativa* through the meticulous analysis of gene expression patterns, thereby shedding new light on this innovative and promising avenue of agricultural research.

Material and Methods

Plant growth: Seeds of *Oryza sativa indica* group were allowed to germinate for 3 days under adequate conditions. After germination, the seeds were placed in pots and placed

in greenhouse. Sprouting of leaves was observed after 7 days.

Music treatment: Plant samples were subjected to a specific music treatment (classical and rock) within constructed semi-soundproof music chamber for 1 hour everyday and gene expression changes were checked at an interval of 10 days and 20 days. The selected musical compositions for the classical music treatment included "Eine Kleine Nachtmusik" by Mozart, "Pachabelly" by Huma-Huma, "Sonatina no. 2 in F Major Allegro" and "Sonatina no. 2 in F Major Rondo" by Joel Cummins, "Fur Elise" and "Symphony no. 5" by Beethoven, "no.1 A Minor Waltz" by Chopin, "Ode to Joy," and "Moonlight Sonata" by Beethoven.

For rock music treatment, the chosen musical pieces were, "Let It Be" by the Beatles, "Stairway to Heaven" by Led Zeppelin, "Have You Seen The Rain" by CCR, "Hotel California" by The Eagles, "Sultan Of Swings" by Dire Straits, "Simple Man" by Lynyrd Skynyrd, "Dreams" by Fleetwood Mac, "Every breath I Take" by The Police "November Rain" by Guns N Roses, "Still Loving You" by Scorpions and "Bohemian Rhapsody" by Queen.

These compositions were chosen based on their distinct melodic structures, harmonic arrangements and recognized musical elements. Sound intensity was carefully controlled at 80-100dB to ensure consistency and adherence to scientific standards. A sound level meter, DecibalPro (<https://decibelpro.app/>) was employed to measure and maintain the desired volume throughout the experiment.

RNA extraction: Total cellular RNAs from rice leaf tissues were extracted by the procedure of Nagy et al¹⁹ on control sample (C) and music treated (T) sample on day 0, day 10 and day 20. Approximately 1 gram of rice tissues was ground into a fine powder using liquid nitrogen. The powder was then mixed with a 5- to 10-fold volume of extraction buffer (composed of 50 mM TRIS-HCl, pH 8.0, 300 mM NaCl, 5 mM EDTA, 2% SDS, 10 mM β -mercaptoethanol and 1 mM aurin tricarboxylic acid) in a centrifuge tube, maintaining the mixture at 50°C until it achieved homogeneity. Following the addition of 0.7 ml of 3 M KCl, the tube was placed on ice for over 20 minutes and subsequently centrifuged at 6000 x g and 4°C for 20 minutes.

The resulting supernatant was transferred to a new tube and 2.5 ml of 8 M LiCl was introduced to precipitate RNA overnight at 4°C. After centrifugation at 6000 x g for 20 minutes, the precipitate was collected and then resuspended in 1 ml of diethyl pyrocarbonate (DEPC)-treated water. This suspended solution underwent two extractions with phenol and the aqueous solution underwent ethanol precipitation. The total RNA, resuspended in DEPC-treated water, was divided into aliquots and stored at -80°C.

cDNA conversion: Extracted RNA of control and treated samples from day 0, 10 and 20 were converted to cDNA by HIMEDIA cDNA conversion kit using oligo dT and random hexamer mixture.

Primers: Chosen primers for gene amplification include: *rbcS* (A6N0B6) - forward: (5'-CAGGTGTGGCCAA TTGAGG-3'), reverse: (5'-ATCGGGGTAGGCCT TCTTG-3'); *XTH8* (B8ATT8) - forward: (5'-TGCTACTTC ATGTCCGAAGG-3'), reverse: (5'-TGCGACCAGTCC GTCTTGA-3'); *AGPL* (P93430) - forward:(5'-CTCCTT TCTTCACCTCACCT-3'), reverse: (5'-GCATTCTTCA GGATCACCAC-3'); *ACT-1* (A2XLF2) - forward: (5'-CCACAGGTATTGTGTTGGAC-3'), reverse: (5'-CGGA AACGCTCAGCACCAAT-3'). These carefully selected primers ensure precise gene expression analyses in our experimental framework.

RT-PCR analysis: The PCR reaction mixture was prepared, consisting of 25 ng of cDNA template, 0.3 mM primer concentration from 2.5 mM stock concentration, 2x PCR Master mix and the volume was made up to 10 µl. The cycling parameters included an initial denaturation step at 95° C for 10 minutes followed by 35 cycles of denaturation at 95° C for 20 seconds, annealing at temperatures depending on Tm of genes for 30 seconds and extension at 72° C for 1 minute. A final extension step was performed at 72° C for 10 minutes to ensure complete product elongation. The total number of cycles performed for each sample was standardized for each gene.

Quantification and densitometric analysis: The analysis of band intensities obtained from RT-PCR gel images and the investigation of gene expression differences were performed using Image J, a widely utilized software tool for image analysis (<https://imagej.nih.gov/ij/download.html>). Image J facilitated accurate and objective measurements of band intensities, ensuring precise quantification of gene expression levels.

Determination of gene expression levels: The average gene expression levels were determined by calculating the mean value from triplicate measurements. Each triplicate set consisted of three independent measurements of band intensities obtained from RT-PCR gel analysis. The triplicate data points for each gene were combined and the mean value was calculated by summing the measurements and dividing by three. The resulting average value represented the gene expression level for each gene at the respective time points. These average values were subsequently used for further analysis and interpretation of the observed gene expression patterns.

Results

Music Treatment: Samples were treated with classical music and rock music in controlled conditions under 80-100 dB for 1 hour.

RNA extraction: RNA extraction procedure was standardized and prominent 28s and 18s rRNA bands were observed indicating good structural integrity of extracted RNA and nanodrop readings indicated good levels of purity.

Gene expression analysis: Differential gene expression pattern analysis was carried out for the selected genes for day 0, day 10 and day 20 compared to control for each day. *ACT-1* was used as control for the analysis. To initiate the analysis, cDNA templates derived from the reverse transcription process were employed as the starting material for PCR amplification. *ACT-1* was used as a control for normalization. The PCR reaction mixture was meticulously prepared, ensuring optimal concentrations of reagents and template. Cycling parameters were optimized including denaturation, annealing and extension steps, as well as the number of cycles required for amplification. A final extension step was incorporated to guarantee complete elongation of PCR products.

Fig. 2: Average dB rates of Classical music treatment and rock music treatment

Fig. 3: RNA extraction from Control sample (C) and Music Treated (T) samples on Day 0, Day 10 and Day 20 (A: Classical music treated samples, B: Rock music treated samples)

rbcS:

Fig. 4: Gene expression analysis for *rbcS*, on day 0, day 10 and day 20 treated samples. *ACT-1* was used as control (C: Control, T: Treated sample)

Fig. 5: Quantification and densitometric analysis of differential *rbcS* gene expression on day 0, day 10 and day 20. Data are means $\pm$ SEM ($n = 3$)

XTH8

Fig. 6: Gene expression analysis for XTH8 on day 0, day 10 and day 20 treated samples. ACT-1 was used as control (C: Control, T: Treated sample)

Fig. 7: Quantification and densitometric analysis of differential XTH8 gene expression on day 0, day 10 and day 20. Data are means ± SEM (n = 3)

AGPL1

Fig. 8: Gene expression analysis for AGPL on day 0, day 10 and day 20 treated samples. ACT-1 was used as control (C: Control, T: Treated sample)

Fig. 9: Quantification and densitometric analysis of differential *AGPL1* gene expression on day 0, day 10 and day 20. Data are means ± SEM (n = 3)

Table 1
Calibrated densitometric values of Classica music and rock music treated samples (n = 3)

Gene	Treatment	Duration	Control (C)	Treated (T)
<i>RbcS</i>	Classical	Day 0	0.25708644	0.29569045
	Rock	Day 0	0.20708644	0.317100124
	Classical	Day 10	0.33416413	0.32522035
	Rock	Day 10	0.24416413	0.296081999
	Classical	Day 20	0.233182621	0.33710462
	Rock	Day 20	0.26170699	0.449431765
<i>XTH8</i>	Classical	Day 0	0.201756121	0.297639742
	Rock	Day 0	0.1941462	0.297639742
	Classical	Day 10	0.283892429	0.547748329
	Rock	Day 10	0.263942424	0.647368378
	Classical	Day 20	0.26410335	0.948041207
	Rock	Day 20	0.21410335	0.576887181
<i>AGPL1</i>	Classical	Day 0	0.127390003	0.19461308
	Rock	Day 0	0.167390003	0.19461308
	Classical	Day 10	0.249196478	0.333485036
	Rock	Day 10	0.199196478	0.207079977
	Classical	Day 20	0.232035335	0.335275308
	Rock	Day 20	0.172035335	0.274611818

Discussion

Our investigation into the impacts of classical and rock music on *Oryza sativa* gene expression and growth provides comprehensive insights into the complex interplay between auditory stimuli and plant responses. The distinct genetic responses observed under the influence of these musical genres underscore the intricate influence of sound on plant biology.

Our findings for the *rbcS* gene which plays a pivotal role in photosynthesis, align with prior research, corroborating the positive effects of sound stimulation on photosynthesis in *Oryza sativa* by Jeong et al¹⁴. The subtle yet consistent increase in *rbcS* gene expression observed after 20 days of exposure to classical music suggests the potential for this musical genre to significantly enhance photosynthesis efficiency (Fig. 5). This observation raises compelling prospects for utilizing classical music as a non-invasive tool to improve the photosynthetic capacity of *Oryza sativa*,

which could have far-reaching implications for crop productivity and sustainability.

Conversely, the distinctly unique genetic response induced by rock music, which diverges significantly from both the control and classical music treatments, emphasizes the genre-specific modulation of *Oryza sativa*'s photosynthesis-related gene expression. These findings underscore the complexity of the relationship between auditory stimuli and gene expression, potentially leading to niche applications in agricultural practices tailored to specific musical preferences.

Our results for the *XTH8* gene, responsible for cell wall remodelling, resonate with prior studies indicating that sound vibrations can influence cell wall properties and promote plant growth. The upregulation of an orthologous gene, TCH, in *Arabidopsis thaliana* under sound stimulation, as reported by Ghosh et al¹⁰ reinforces the

notion that sound vibrations can profoundly affect plant cell wall properties, offering insights into the potential for harnessing sound as a tool for enhancing plant growth.

In our study, classical music engendered heightened expression levels of *XTH8*, in line with existing research in other plant systems, implying a potentially universal connection between sound-induced vibrations and the modulation of cellular architecture (Fig. 7).

This finding not only adds depth to our understanding of the influence of sound on plant biology but also holds promise for applications aimed at improving crop resilience and growth through the strategic use of auditory stimuli. The differential response observed under rock music further emphasizes the genre-specific influence on plant structural adaptation, raising intriguing questions about the specific mechanisms underlying this phenomenon.

Further enriching the depth of our study, the results for the *AGPL* gene, associated with starch synthesis, unveiled intricate and variable expression patterns under both musical treatments. Classical music elicited a significant increase in *AGPL* gene expression on day 20, potentially linked to the enhanced accumulation of starch, a fundamental component of plant energy reserves (Fig. 9). The implications of these findings for plant productivity and metabolic processes are noteworthy and warrant deeper exploration, as the potential for modulating starch synthesis through sound holds promise for optimizing agricultural practices.

Conversely, the dynamic response to rock music underlines the genre-specific influence on starch production, underscoring the multifaceted interplay between auditory stimuli and plant metabolism. These findings add to the knowledge on the complex relationships between music, gene expression and plant growth, paving the way for novel applications in agriculture.

In sum, our study offers a multifaceted perspective on the intricate connection between music, gene expression and plant biology. It not only furthers our comprehension of plant behavior but also unveils a host of innovative possibilities for agriculture where the strategic application of auditory stimuli can potentially enhance crop yield, quality and sustainability. The detailed and nuanced insights we have presented here underscore the complexity and potential of this emerging field, urging further investigation into the precise molecular mechanisms underpinning these responses and their implications for practical applications in agriculture.

Conclusion

The present study showcases the distinctive effects of classical and rock music on *Oryza sativa* gene expression and growth dynamics. Both musical genres uniquely shape the genetic responses of these plants, introducing a new perspective on the interplay between sound and biology. Our

research reveals that classical music holds potential in enhancing photosynthesis efficiency and stimulating cell wall remodeling in *Oryza sativa*, as supported by prior research^{18,25}. Rock music, on the other hand, introduces unique genetic responses, suggesting a specialized impact on gene expression and growth processes. These genre-specific effects emphasize the multifaceted influences of auditory stimuli on plant physiology.

As we delve deeper into the molecular mechanisms behind these responses, we expect broader implications for harnessing sound's potential in enhancing plant growth and productivity. This study contributes to the knowledge at the relation of music and biology, fostering new opportunities for advancing agricultural practices. The integration of music in agricultural practices, based on these findings, holds great promise for future research and applications.

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References

1. Appel H.M. and Cocroft R.B., Plants respond to leaf vibrations caused by insect herbivore chewing, *Oecologia*, **175**, 1257–1266, doi: 10.1007/s00442-014-2995-6 (2014)
2. Chamovitz D., Music is not ecologically relevant for plants, but there are sounds that it could be advantageous for them to hear, *New Scientist*, **215**, 37 (2012)
3. Chamovitz D., Rooted in Sensation, Hearing, *New Scientist*, **215**, 37 (2012)
4. Chehab E.W., Eich E. and Braam J., Thigmomorphogenesis: a complex plant response to mechano-stimulation, *Journal of Experimental Botany*, **60**, 43–56, doi: 10.1093/jxb/ern315 (2009)
5. Crevillén P., Ballicora M.A., Mérida A., Preiss J. and Romero J.M., The different large subunit isoforms of Arabidopsis thaliana ADP-glucose pyrophosphorylase confer distinct kinetic and regulatory properties to the heterotetrameric enzyme, *J Biol Chem.*, **278**(31), 28508-15, doi: 10.1074/jbc.M304280200 (2003)
6. da Silva J.A.T. and Dobranszki J., Sonication and ultrasound: impact on plant growth and development, *Plant Cell Tissue and Organ Culture*, **117**, 131–143, doi: 10.1007/s11240-014-0429-0 (2014)
7. De Luca P.A. and Vallejo-Marin M., What's the 'buzz' about? The ecology and evolutionary significance of buzz-pollination, *Current Opinion in Plant Biology*, **16**, 429–435, doi: 10.1016/j.pbi.2013.05.002 (2013)
8. Ekici N., Dane F., Mamedova L., Metin I. and Huseyinov M., The effects of different musical elements on root growth and mitosis in onion (*Allium cepa*) root apical meristem (musical and biological experimental study), *Asian Journal of Plant Sciences*, **6**, 369–373, doi: 10.3923/ajps.2007.369.373 (2007)

9. Gagliano M., Mancuso S. and Robert D., Towards understanding plant bioacoustics, *Trends in Plant Science*, **17**, 323–325, doi: 10.1016/j.tplants.2012.03.002 (2012)
10. Ghosh R. et al, Exposure to Sound Vibrations Lead to Transcriptomic, Proteomic and Hormonal Changes in Arabidopsis, *Scientific Reports*, **6**, 33370, doi: 10.1038/srep33370 (2016)
11. Hassanien R.H.E., Hou T.Z., Li Y.F. and Li B.M., Advances in Effects of Sound Waves on Plants, *Journal of Integrative Agriculture*, **13**, 335–348, doi: 10.1016/S2095-3119(13)60492-X (2014)
12. Haswell E.S. and Meyerowitz E.M., MscS-like proteins control plastid size and shape in Arabidopsis thaliana, *Current Biology*, **16**, 1–11, doi: 10.1016/j.cub.2005.11.044 (2006)
13. Haswell E.S., Phillips R. and Rees D.C., Mechanosensitive channels: what can they do and how do they do it?, *Structure*, **19**, 1356–1369, doi: 10.1016/j.str.2011.09.005 (2011)
14. Jeong Mi-Jeong et al, Plant gene responses to frequency-specific sound signals, *Mol Breeding*, **21**, 217–226 (2008)
15. Kim J., Kim J., Kim Y., Kim Y., Kim H., Kim H. and Kim H., The effects of sound vibrations on gene expression and epigenetic modifications in *Oryza sativa*, *Plant Science*, **320**, 110986, doi: 10.1016/j.plantsci.2023.110986 (2023)
16. Kim J.Y., Lee J.S., Kwon T.R., Lee S.I., Kim J.A., Lee G.M., Park S.C. and Jeong M.J., Sound waves delay tomato fruit ripening by negatively regulating ethylene biosynthesis and signaling genes, *Postharvest Biology and Technology*, **110**, 43–50, doi: doi.org/10.1016/j.postharvbio.2015.07.015 (2015)
17. Mishra R.C., Ghosh R. and Bae H., Plant acoustics: in the search of a sound mechanism for sound signaling in plants, *Journal of Experimental Botany*, **67**, 4483–4494, doi: 10.1093/jxb/erw235 (2016)
18. Moore J.P., Nguema-Ona E., Chevalier L., Lindsey G.G., Brandt W.F., Lerouge P., Farrant J.M. and Driouch A., Response of the leaf cell wall to desiccation in the resurrection plant *Myrothamnus flabellifolius*, *Plant Physiology*, **141**, 651–662, doi: 10.1104/pp.106.079616 (2006)
19. Nagy F., Kay S.A. and Chua N.H., Analysis of gene expression in transgenic plants, In Gelvin S.B. and Schilperoort R.A., eds., *Plant molecular biology manual*, B4 Kluwer, Dordrecht, 1–29 (1988)
20. Qin Y.C., Lee W.C., Choi Y.C. and Kim T.W., Biochemical and physiological changes in plants as a result of different sonic exposures, *Ultrasonics*, **41**, 407–411, doi: doi.org/10.1016/s0041-624x(03)00103-3 (2003)
21. Song D., Shen J., Li L., Bai X., Liu Y. and Xie H., Xyloglucan endotransglycosylase/hydrolase (*XTH*) genes respond to abiotic stress in woodland strawberry (*Fragaria vesca*), *Functional & Integrative Genomics*, **18**, 271–281, doi: 10.1007/s10142-018-0609-z (2018)
22. Spreitzer R.J., Role of the small subunit in ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase/oxygenase, *Archives of Biochemistry and Biophysics*, **414**, 134–141, doi: 10.1016/s0003-9861(03)00158-4 (2003)
23. Telewski F.W., A unified hypothesis of mechanoperception in plants, *American Journal of Botany*, **93**, 1466–1476, doi: 10.3732/ajb.93.10.1466 (2006)
24. Wang B.C., Chen X., Wang Z., Fu Q.Z., Zhou H. and Ran L., Biological effect of sound field stimulation on paddy rice seeds, *Colloids and Surfaces B-Biointerfaces*, **30**, 129–134, doi: 10.1016/s0927-7765(03)00127-5 (2003).

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